

THE ROLE OF NATIONAL FESTIVALS IN THE LIFE OF COMMUNITY

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Abstract. *In many places around the globe cultural festivals have been started as essential forms of social and cultural participation. Furthermore, is relatively new ritual to many places (Guerra et al., 2016). According to Cudny et al., Festivals are becoming an integral part of the culture and nation. Their musical and colourful atmosphere attracts people from all over the world(2013). Festivals have been an old tradition in many cultures. However, now is the main cultural product of modern times which play a role in the development of the stave. Festivals show the uniqueness of a culture which can show the whole world the traditions of a nation. The purpose of the article is to describe the features and behavior of increase the attractiveness of Central Asia.*

Key words: *history, Importance of Festivals, Role of Festival, Festivals.*

Аннотация. *Во многих странах мира культурные фестивали стали важнейшими формами социального и культурного участия. Кроме того, это относительно новый ритуал для многих мест (Guerra et al. 2016). По мнению Кадни и др., фестивали становятся неотъемлемой частью культуры и нации. Их музыкальная и красочная атмосфера привлекает людей со всего мира (2013). Фестивали были древней традицией во многих культурах. Однако сейчас это главным культурным продуктом современности, который играет роль в развитии. Фестивали демонстрируют уникальность культуры, которая может показать всему миру традиции нации. Цель статьи - описать особенности и поведение повышения привлекательности Центральной Азии.*

Ключевые слова: *история, Значение фестивалей, Роль фестивалей, Фестивали.*

Annotatsiya. *Dunyoning ko'plab mamlakatlarida madaniy festivallar eng muhim shakllariga aylandi ijtimoiy va madaniy ishtirok o'z ichiga olgan. Bundan tashqari, bu ko'p joylarda nisbatan yangi marosimdir. (Guerra va boshq. 2016). Cudney va boshqalarga ko'ra, festivallar ajralmas qismiga aylanmoqda madaniyat va millat. Ularning musiqiy va rang-barang muhiti har tomondan odamlarni o'ziga jalb qiladi butun dunyodan (2013). Festivallar ko'plab madaniyatlarda qadimiy an'ana bo'lib kelgan. Biroq, hozir shunday taraqqiyotida rol o'ynaydigan zamonamizning asosiy madaniy mahsuloti. Festivallar butun dunyoga ko'rsata oladigan madaniyatni, o'ziga xosligini namoyish etadigan xalq an'analardiri. Maqolaning maqsadi festivallarning xususiyatlari va xatti-harakatlarni tasvirlashdir va markaziy osiyoning jozibadorligini oshirish.*

Kalit so'zlar: *tarix, Bayramlarning ma'nosi, Bayramlarning o'rni, Festivallar.*

INTRODUCTION

Festivals and various holidays have become a part of our lives. They force us to learn new interesting traditions that combine many historical origins, investigate deeply the nations, culture and their unique traditions. "Festivals are cultural celebration and have always occupied a special in societies" (Getz, 2010). They combine not only traditions, but also national music and a unique and unforgettable atmosphere. We must show the world our traditions and culture through our

beautiful festivals. This article demonstrates the significance of festivals in our lives, about their origins and roles. As well as, the importance of the need for festivals. It is supplemented then by authors with the most interesting festivals in Asian countries.

Festivals: Origins and Meaning

According to Nikolaeva et al. in Russia, the soil for the emergence and development of festivals was the emergence of the October Revolution in 1917. The Soviet culture was in urgent need of new colorful festivals that could be contrasted with pre-revolutionary culture. The introduction of new ideals was of great importance for the consolidation of socialist system. It was also important to find a unifying beginning for the new Soviet state, striving to reunite the people after the civil war.(2008) It was very important to find holidays that would unite different nations and cultures. Because it was the beginning for the new Soviet state. They played a leading role in the life of the nation so that ordinary people learned deeply about their own traditions as well as the traditions of other nations. Festivals helped people to come together again and spend time to go deep into history and learn more. The festivals of the peoples of Central Asia are so rich that they are of many kinds such as dance, theater, circus, music, ballet and others.

Importance and role of festival

In these times of the twenty –first century , festivals have managed to become an integral part of our life. Every year, more than a hundred different events are held all over the world. Festivals attract people with their unconventionality, and sometimes even absurdity. “It helps us to keep connected to our roots, our culture, our values, our origin and to preserve it” (Fahimuddin, 2019). The festival can act as an integrator in the community, both local and professional Creative a communicative, social and psychological space in the city. As part of the festive culture, the festival serves as a ritual. It promotes new cultural values and meaning in society. (Topkan. et al., 1985). The role of the festivals as a ritual is realized by the participants of festival especially by the organizers and the professional of the community. The festival help to learn about the past and realize what has changed over the years.

Interesting Festivals.

Navruz is considered a Muslim holiday. For Muslims this is a very important holiday because for them it is New year. The festival is actually celebrated for several days, with the first day, 21st of March being the main day. Name of Navruz means "the new day" from Persian language. This holiday is popular not only in Uzbekistan but in other Muslim countries like Tajikistan, Kyrgyzstan, Kazakhstan, Turkmenistan, Azerbaijan, Afghanistan, Turkey, Iran etc. Navruz symbolizes purity, friendship between nations, love and happiness. People wear their beautiful traditional clothes on this day. People try to be more kind, help each other, go to visit relatives. A feature of this holiday is that it helps people be merciful on this day. Elderly still spend a very long time preparing for these holidays, usually they clean their house, clothes, streets which they live in and pay all their debts. Some of these rituals came from ancient times by Zorostrism ideology and people still believe that once upon a time the Zorostrism came up with this holiday but there is no evidence. Navruz brings people better feelings and peace. Usually, traditional dishes are prepared for this holiday such as samsa, dumplings, pilaf, shurba and two signature dishes, Sumalak and Khalisa. Khalisa is made from lamb and is usually cooked all day long. Sumalak means 30 angels. There is a legend that when sumalak is prepared, 30 angels will sit around. The main ingredient of this dish is wheat and is cooked approximately one day and night. It is such a wonderful custom that everyone gets together and celebrates this holiday.

Indians Holi festival is another vary prominent holiday celebrated in March, when nature blooms after hibernation. Holi is celebrated not only by Indians but a lot of other countries like Bangladesh, Pakistan, South Africa, Malaysia and United States. This colourful festival attracts more and more tourists around the world with its unique parties, dances, concert and events. According to Bednarz et al., “the colourful party makes up just one part of Holi. The night before on Holika Dahan which means the evening of bonfires, revelers set a symbolic effigy ablaze to commemorate the demise of the demoness Holiks. People throw the famed, colored powder on Rangwali Holi, the second and most famous day of the festival” (2023). This festival is celebrated for 3 days but in some part of India it continues for up to 16 days. Children and adults wear clean white clothes. And from early morning they will start pouring different colors on each other. These colours bring brightness and cheerfulness to people." The tradition of throwing colored powder and water is believed to originate from the mythological love story of Radha and Krishna. Krishna, the Hindu god depicted with dark blue skin is believed to have complained to his mother about Radhas fair complexion. To ease her sons sadness, his mother suggests he Radhas skin colour by smearing her with paint. Its believed that is where the custom of smearing loved ones with colour during Holi come from" (Suri et al., 2019). People believed that their god Krishna invented this holiday many years ago. Indians take a long time to prepare, by painting and decorating their houses. They also prepare various traditional dishes on this day.

The Boseong Green Tea Festival is held every May at Daehan Dawon, the town's most famous green tea plantation. Visitors can enjoy a variety of activities, including tea-picking, tea-roasting and tea-making. Daily events include a tea art festival, tea ceremony, hanbok fashion show, concerts, picking tea leaves and a tour of green tea fields. Visitors can also make their own tea, tea bowls, green tea rice cakes and green tea soap” (Redmond. et al, n.d) Tea is famous not only in Korea, but also in all Asian countries. Therefore, tourist come from all around the world to celebrate this festival. Acording to Crancy et al., “the origins of the festival date back to the 7th century when tea seeds were first brought to Korea from China. It was in Boseong County, nestled in the picturesque hills of Jeollanam-do, that green tea found its perfect home. The region's ideal climate and fertile soil proved to be the perfect breeding ground for the cultivation of green tea, a beverage that quickly became a staple of Korean culture. For centuries, the people of Boseong have tended to their tea plantations, carefully nurturing and cultivating the tea leaves that have come to represent their way of life. It was in the spirit of this deep appreciation for green tea that the Boseong Green Tea Festival was first held in 1980” (2023). After this, a large green tea plantation still remains in Beseong. This holiday is held to spread medicinal green tea. Korean green tea is more expensive and tastier than other teas. People are willing to pay for original Korean green tea.

Chinese New Year or Chunjie Spring Festival. This is most popular and important holiday not only in China but also in Thailand, Malaysia, Indonesia, Singapore and Mauritius. “The history of the Chinese New Year festival can be traced back to about 3,500 years ago. Chinese New Year has evolved over a long period of time and its customs have undergone a long developmental process. The date of the Chinese New Year is determined by the lunar calendar. The holiday falls on the second new moon after the winter solstice on December 21. Each year the New Year in China falls on a different date than on the Gregorian calendar. The dates usually range sometime between January 21 and February 20”(Timothy et al., n.d) Chinese New Year is considered a very important family holiday. On this day, every family member should be at home, the Chinese wear their traditional clothes, try not to keep garbage at home and keep everything

clean at home. They prepare many traditional dishes and dine at the place. A very important part is concerts with dragons, dances, and various decorations. On this day people go to visit relatives and friends. People still celebrate this holiday as a new year. This holiday is very similar to our Navruz. Festivals are very important for us, each of them has a deep meaning, they help us to see love and happiness in each other's eyes again, help to get together again and learn more about history. Moreover, the way how they attract tourists to their country like concerts with dragons dances is a way which we can be apply to Uzbekistan. For example, spiritual bird "Humo" symbolizes peace and happiness and it is applicable to this example. We may organize Humo bird dance demonstrated during Navruz to be a destination chosen by hordes of travelers to come and see the culture and tradition.

CONCLUSIONS

Festivals are a culture phenomenon that develop within a historical context. Holidays and festivals help us delve deeper into our history and nation. While many traditions are forgotten, festivals make us aware of our culture. Humanity needs festivals without them our life is boring and without colour. "Visitors told that attending a cultural festival improved their well-being and work ability" (Haahti et al, 2015). People now spend a lot of time at work and are too tied up in everyday life. Festivals, with their colorfulness, help us relax, learn new information, make us feel new emotions that help us forget about sadness and think only about good things. Each of them has its own deep meaning, including different traditions, music, clothes and dances; they motivate us to be happy. In order to preserve culture and customs coupled with history and traditions we should follow traditions and not only celebrate, but also promote and market our national festivals and celebrations to attract more tourists to Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Bednarz, Ch. (2023) Inside Holi Festival one of Indians most colorful Hindu tradition. National Geographic.
2. Crancy, L. (2023) The Rich History and Culture of Green tea at the Boseong Green tea Festival in Korea. Korea travel.
3. Cudny, W. (2013) Festival Tourism the concept, key functions and Dysfunction in the context of tourism. *Geographical Journal*, 65(2), 105-118
4. Fahimuddin, D. (2019) Celebrity of festivals and Cultural Appreciation. Department of Education.
5. Gat, D. (2010) The nature and scope of festival studies. *International Journal of Event Management Research*.
6. Guerra, P. (2016) From the night and the light, all festivals are golden: The festivalization of culture in the late modernity. *Foundation for Science and Technology*.
7. Haahti, A. (2015) Visitor discourse on experiences reasons for festival success and failure. *International Journal of Event and Festival Management*. 6(3)251-268.
8. Nikolaeva, V. (2008) Фестиваль как этап эволюции праздничной культуры. *Культурная жизнь Юго России*, 27(2) 2008 144-146
9. Redmond, J. (n.d) Boseong to host green tea festival. The Korea Times.
10. Suri, M. (2019) The legend behind the festival of color. Discovery Company CNN travel.
11. Timothy, S. (n.d) History of Chinese New Year. Wake Forest University Museum of Anthropology.